

ML species tree generated from 216AA data set and LG method.

ML species tree generated from 216AA data set and MF+MERGE method.

ML species tree generated from 216NT_Degen data set.

ML species tree generated from 550AA data set.

ML species tree generated from 550NT_Degen data set.

MP species tree generated from 216AA data set.

MP species tree generated from 550AA data set.

MP species tree generated from 216NT_Degen data set.

MP species tree generated from 550NT_Degen data set.